

A Study on Consumer Preferences towards Pendrive in Theni District

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Abstract

A USB flash drive is a data storage device that includes flash memory with an integrated Universal Serial Bus (USB) interface. USB flash drives are typically removable and rewritable, and physically much smaller than a floppy disk. Most weigh less than 30 gram. This paper entitled “A study on consumer preference and satisfaction towards Pen drive with special reference to Theni” is carried out with an objective to determine the consumer preference and satisfaction. The primary objective of this study is to find out the consumer preference and satisfaction towards pen drive with special reference to Theni. The secondary data was collected from related websites, books. For distribution of questionnaire to the consumer convenience sampling method was used to select the customer and the survey was taken among those selected users. After collecting the data from the respondents it was analyzing using simple percentage method for analyzing the collected data. To identify the factors customer to buy pen drive. To know the customer satisfaction towards the repeated purchase of particular Pen Drive in Theni District.

Keywords: consumer preferences and satisfaction, uses

Introduction

A USB flash drive is a data storage device that includes flash memory with an integrated Universal Serial Bus (USB) interface. USB flash drives are typically removable and rewritable, and physically much smaller than a floppy disk. Most weigh less than 30 gram. As of January 2013 drives of 1 terabytes (TB) are available, and storage capacities as large as 2 terabytes are planned, with steady improvements in size and price per capacity expected. Some allow up to 1,00,000 write/erase cycles (depending on the exact type memory chip used) and 10 years shelf storage time.

USB flash drives are often used for the same purposes for which floppy disks or CDROMs were used. They are smaller, faster, have thousands of times more capacity, and are more durable and reliable because they have no moving parts. Until approximately 2005, most desktop and laptop computers were supplied with floppy disk drives, but floppy disk drives have been abandoned in favour of USB. This paper mainly focused on the consumer preferences towards pen drive in Theni.

Uses of Pendrive System Administrators' Helper

System and network administrators find USB pen drive highly handy to load them with configuration information and software used for system maintenance, troubleshooting, and recovery. Such use of this portable device makes it popular among them.

As an Application Carrier

USB pen drives are used to carry applications that run on the host computer without the necessity of installation. U3, backed by pen drive vendors, offers an API to pen drive-specific functions. Portableapps, a free and open-source software, has also been developed to allow U3 drives. Air WRX is also an application framework that runs from a pen drive and turns its PC host and other nearby PCs into a multi-screen, web-like work environment.

As Audio Players

A number of companies make solid state digital audio players in a small form factor, essentially producing pen drives with sound output and a simple user interface. The MP3 playback function is the most popular addition to USB pen Drive. Some of them also have LCD display for track browsing and audio input jack and rechargeable battery.

Review of Literature

John 2008 in his Study analyzed that it is the youth which is the real growth driver of the technology industry in India. Considering this fact the paper is an attempt to give a snapshot of how frequently young people use their pen drives for several embodied functions of the pen drive. Data was collected from a sample of 200 people aged between 20 and 29. The study sheds light on how gender, influence the usage pattern of this device. Findings of the study would be helpful for the pen drive manufacturers to formulate marketing segments.

Ragul 2008 in his study titled "A Study of pen drive usage among the post graduates students" analyzed that it is important for Pen drive carriers, developers, equipments manufacturers as well as parents and young people alike that the key characteristics of Pen drive technology is well understood. So that the risks associated with its potentially damaging or disruptive aspects can be mitigated. This paper has tried to compare the usage difference by gender with respect to the difference manufacturing companies.

Rakesh 2006 in their study analyzed that majority of the respondents have given favorable opinion towards the pen drive brands but some problems exist that deserve the attention of the pen drive manufacturers. They need to bridge gap between the product promised and product offered. The overall customer's attitude towards pen drive brands is that they are satisfied with the existing brands but still they want more brands to be provided. John 2008 in his Study analyzed that it is the youth which is the real growth driver of the technology industry in India. Considering this fact the paper is an attempt to give a snapshot of how frequently young people use their pen drives for several embodied functions of the pen drive..

Data Collection Technique

The present study is completely based on primary data by adopting questionnaire method. Questionnaire is a set of questions that the respondent has to answer. The answer will be tabulated, analysed and final conclusions will be drawn from it. Questionnaire was issued collected from the consumer of Chennai.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is to find the behaviour of the consumer regarding the quality, price and usage of pen drive. This study is limited to the capability of the respondents appropriately answering the questions, the study is conducted on 50 customers selected by sampling methods. The study is of studying to customer's "behaviour and satisfaction towards pen drives/USB flash drives".

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study are:

- To analyse the opinion of consumers behaviour towards usage of pen drives/USB flash drives.
- To make a competitive analysis on various brands of pen drives.
- To know the opinion of the consumer’s regarding the price, quality and usage.
- To know the customers readiness towards innovative products.
- To offer suggestion and conclusion based on the study.

Analysis and Interpretation

The research has used the simple percentage analysis and diagrammatic presentation of data.

Table Age wise classification of the sample respondents

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage of respondents(100)
12-16	3	6%
17-21	25	50%
21-25	13	26%
Above 25 years	9	18%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data

Table shows the age wise classification of the sample respondent. This table implies that among 50 respondents 6% (3) are in the age group of 12 to 16; 50% (25) are in the age group of 17 to 21; 26% (13) are of 21 25; And 18% (9) are in the group of above 25 years. The pen drive is most effectively used by the members who are in the age group of 17 to 21 years.

Table Brands of pen drives preferred by the sample respondents

Brand	Number of Respondents (50)	Percentage of respondents (100)
Kingston	2	4%
Sony	10	20%
Transcend	10	20%
Sandisk	8	16%
HP	20	40%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data

Table influences the brands of pen drives that are preferred by the sample respondents. Among the 50 respondents 4% (2) of the respondents prefer to use Kingston brand pen drives; 20% (10) of the respondents are preferably using Sony brand; 20% (10) of them are preferring the brand of Transcend; 16% (8) of them are using Sandisk pen drives; and 40% (20) of the respondents are using HP brand of pen drives. The pen drives are mostly preferable in the HP brand.

Table Storage capacity of the pen drives used by sample respondents

Storage	Number of respondents (50)	Percentage of respondents(100)
2GB	0	0%
4GB	11	22%
8GB	10	20%
16GB	22	44%
32GB	4	8%
64GB	3	6%
Total	50	100%

Source: Primary data

Table depicts the storage capacity of the pen drives that is being used by the sample respondents. Among the 50 respondents 2 GB is used by 0%(0);22%(11) of the respondents are using 4 GB pen drives; 20%(10) of the respondents are using 8GB capacity; 16GB is used by 44% (22)of the respondents; and 8(4)of the respondents using 32GB pen drivesand 64 GB is used by the 6%(3). From the above it is clear that the drives having storage capacity of 16 GB is widely used by the respondents.

Table Purpose of using the pen drive by the sample respondents

Purpose	Number of respondents (50)	Percentage of Respondents (100)
Entertainment	8	16%
For studies	28	56%
For professional use	11	22%
Others	3	6%
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table describes the purpose of using pen drives by the sample respondents. Among the 50 respondents 16% (8) of the respondents are using their pen drive for Studies;22% (11) of the purpose;56% (28) of the respondents are using their pen drive for professional use; and 6% (3) of the respondents are using their pen drive for other purposes. Among the above purposes Pen drives are mainly and mostly used for studies.

Findings

- It is found that the majority of 17-21 age group are playing a vital role in the usage of pen drive.
- It is found that the HP brand is having a high recognition rate.
- It is found that the highest storage capacity of pen drives used by the sample respondents is 16 GB
- Most of the respondents are used their pen drive mainly for the purpose of studies.

Conclusion

The collected data was analyzed using simple percentage and Bar charts. Certain factors which inhabit and facilities te customer preference of the availability and reduce the price were found out. Based on the inferences drawn certain suggestion have been recommended. In this study an attempt is made to measure the customer analysis and preference about these brands. It is found that customers are satisfied with their brands.

The company should overcome the problems in the usage of the pen drives. Still it has to create awareness to all to make the usage of pen drive still more effective. Based on this study it is clear that maximum the students are making use of pen dries. And they are Often suffering from the problem of infection of Anti virus. So the company should implement more innovative ideas for promoting the product and to achieve more usage of it.

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